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Technology dEsiGn In sub saharan afriCa
(STRATEGIC)**

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STRATEGIC's Responsible Research and Innovation Approach

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Abstract	This deliverable summarises insights into current Responsible Research and Innovation approaches in Europe and Africa whilst highlighting emerging concepts of an approach that aligns with African contexts, interests and realities.
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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
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EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
VSD	Value Sensitive Design
AREA	Anticipate, Reflect, Engage, Act
STI	Science, Technology, and Innovation
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
STS	Science and Technology Studies
TA	Technology Assessment
ELSA	Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Implications
DSIT	Department for Science, Innovation and Technology
EDCTP	The European & Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership
EbD	Ethics-by-Design
AU	African Union
EU	European Union
NEC	National Ethics Committees
REC	National Regulatory Authorities
DHT	Digital health technologies
ICT	Information and communication technology
CAIR	South Africa's Centre for Artificial Intelligence Research
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
CSO	Civil society organizations
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises

STRATEGIC	Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital health Technology dEsiGn In subsaharan afriCa
UON	University of Nottingham
LETS	Université de Yaoundé
LUMSA	Libera Università degli Studi Maria Ss. Assunta di Roma
AI	Artificial intelligence

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Executive Summary

The deliverable outlines the conceptual foundation and practical orientation of responsible research and innovation (RRI) that should shape digital health technologies for clinical trials and research. It provides a comparative review of existing RRI frameworks in Europe; such as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), the AREA framework, Value Sensitive Design (VSD), and Ethics-by-Design and evaluates their uptake and limitations within African research and innovation ecosystems. It also explores emerging RRI initiatives across the African continent, including community-based health innovation, participatory AI ethics and governance, and data justice movements. Drawing on these insights, the deliverable introduces a preliminary framework for a context-sensitive, decolonial, and values-driven African approach to responsible innovation. This emerging African model emphasises communal ethics, epistemic plurality, relational accountability, and local agency, but more so, seeks to move beyond the adaptation of Eurocentric models toward a co-created, localised, and justice-centred paradigm. The preliminary framework sets the stage for STRATEGIC's operationalisation of responsible innovation across clinical research and capacity-building activities in Africa, ensuring alignment with both global standards and African ethical traditions, innovation priorities, and socio-technical realities.

1. Introduction

The notion of responsible innovation (RI) has become central theme across industries and sectors of the global economy. The responsible research and innovation approach has been identified as critical in ethics reviews and evaluation of digital health technology because it often goes beyond conventional checklists and anticipates broader societal implications, ensuring that innovation aligns with public values, needs, and rights. Responsible innovation as an approach seeks to ensure that science, technology, and innovation are developed in ways that are ethically acceptable, socially desirable, legally compliant, and sustainable. It emphasizes the alignment of research and innovation with societal values, needs, and expectations. According to Stilgoe et al., (2013), RI is about "taking care of the future through collective stewardship of science and innovation in the present."

Unlike traditional innovation models that focus primarily on technical progress or market oriented success, RI approaches focus on 'responsibility' from the onset; integrating ethical, legal, and social considerations into every stage of the innovation lifecycle, from design, development to deployment. The responsible innovation approach goes beyond simply seeking technological advancement and economic gain, instead focusing on the wider impacts of innovation on society and the environment.

There are many reasons why responsible innovation is critically important in the ethics review of digital health technologies. One of these reasons is that it is an approach that anticipates unintended consequences. Digital health technologies, like AI diagnostics, health apps, or wearable trackers, can have far-reaching effects beyond their immediate clinical research and practice uses. By anticipating potential harm (e.g., privacy issues, misuse of technology), organisations or research teams can be proactive rather than reactive; taking steps to prevent or minimise them from the outset, rather than trying to fix problems later. Another reason is that RI encourages the involvement of relevant stakeholders into the process of innovation; stakeholders whose needs are being served, who might often be marginalised or harmed. Engaging with stakeholders who are often denied any meaningful involvement and being transparent about the innovation process helps build public trust in new technologies and the organisations that develop them. This is vital for the long-term acceptance and success of innovations. RRI processes ensures responsiveness and adaptability to new context and cultures. As the digital health technology landscape is constantly

evolving, the RRI approach supports ongoing evaluation and iterative changes, enabling the technology to be adapted in response to real-world outcomes, improved as cultural norms and/or evidence change. This allows the ethics review process to be dynamic and not static. Consequently, RRI process promotes reflexivity where researchers or innovators reflect on their assumptions and existing power dynamics. Digital health technologies like other emerging technologies often reinforce global power imbalances, the RRI approach helps to challenge existing social divides and promote digital justice and pluriversal perspectives.

In summary, a responsible innovation approach ensures that ethics reviews are forward-looking, participatory, and context-sensitive, which is vital in digital health due to the complex interplay of technology, human well-being, and societal values. Across sectors of the economy, it is evident that RI approaches supports the ethical, legal, and social acceptability of innovations in ways that traditional approaches may overlook.

2. History of RRI

It is important to note that Responsible Innovation encompasses all forms of innovation, including in industry, design, entrepreneurship, policy, and civil society, not limited to academic or research contexts. However, when it narrowly focuses on research-driven innovation, particularly within publicly funded scientific research and academia, it is often referred to as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Whilst the concept of RRI is relatively recent, it is philosophically and theoretically rooted in critical studies that have long questioned the neutrality of science and technology. The foundational influences of RRI can be traced to overlapping traditions in ethics, science policy, and technology assessment (Shelley-Egan, Gjefsen and Nydal, 2020; Yaghmaei et al., 2024). These include:

Scholarship in Science and Technology Studies (STS) where scholars like Sheila Jasanoff (2005), Bruno Latour (2000), and Steve Woolgar (1991) have interrogated how science and technology are socially constructed and shaped by power relations, politics, and values. Related works in Technology Assessment (TA) (Banta, 2009; Grunwald, 2009), aimed to anticipate and evaluate the societal impacts of emerging technologies. The Precautionary Principle (Foster, Vecchia and Repacholi, 2000; Kriebel et al., 2001) has gained prominence in environmental and biomedical ethics during the 1980s and 1990s, advocating for caution and foresight in the face of scientific uncertainty (e.g., GMOs, biotechnology). Additionally, bioethics and research ethics studies, particularly in response to scandals like the Tuskegee syphilis study and debates around nuclear energy, underscored the need for responsibility in scientific conduct.

The concept of RRI draws from ideas of anticipatory governance (Barben et al., 2008) which advocates for a forward-looking, participatory, and reflexive governance of emerging technologies. This is partly due to the Collingridge Dilemma (Genus and Stirling, 2018) - the idea that it's hard to control technology after it becomes entrenched, but hard to predict its impact in early stages, hence the need for early societal engagement.

However, the concept of RRI was formalised and popularised through European Union (EU) science policy, particularly as part of the Horizon 2020 framework (Tabarés et al., 2022). RRI was explicitly adopted as a cross-cutting theme in Horizon 2020 by the European Commission. This process identified 6 key pillars of Public Engagement, Gender Equality, Science Education, Ethics, Open Access, and Governance. To add to this, some Horizon 2020 projects were specifically focussed on exploring ways of operationalising and embedding RRI practices in research institutions, industry and policy. These include [RESPONSIBILITY](#)¹, [RRI Tools](#)², [PRISMA](#)³, and [GREAT](#):

The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) was also among the first research councils to formally adopt RRI language and principles. A turning point came in the early 2010s, particularly through the development of the AREA framework by Stilgoe, Owen and Macnaghten (2013). AREA stands for:

- Anticipate – What are the potential impacts (intended and unintended) of the research?
- Reflect – What are the purposes of the research? What assumptions are being made?
- Engage – Who might be affected, and how can they be involved?
- Act – How can the research process or direction be modified in response?

The EPSRC embraced this framework to guide researchers in embedding responsibility throughout the research lifecycle, not just as an add-on. Furthermore, Jirotko et al., (2017) developed the "4Ps" to offer a complementary way to understand and implement RRI principles. The 4Ps stand for Product (what is being developed), Purpose (why is it being developed?), Process (how is it being developed?) and People (who is involved and who is affected?). Together, the AREA and 4Ps frameworks give diverse researchers

¹ <https://responsibility-rri.eu/the-project/overview/#:~:text=The%20RESPONSIBILITY%20project%20aims%20to,Europe%20and%20around%20the%20globe.>

² <https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/projects/rri-tools>

³ <https://www.rri-prisma.eu/>

practical entry points for thinking about the societal dimensions of their work.

3. Critique of RRI

Despite its wider implementation in research and practice, some researchers believe that translating RRI principles into practice has proved difficult (Felt, 2017; van Hove and Wickson, 2017), especially in industry or fast-paced innovation settings like AI or digital health (Patel and and Moreau, 2024). RRI often remains theoretical or symbolic, not embedded in the day-to-day work of scientists or engineers. Many researchers and practitioners lack training or time to meaningfully engage in anticipation, reflection, and stakeholder engagement (Bamzai-Dodson and and McPherson, 2024). This is suggesting that there's often a mismatch between the rhetoric of RRI and its actual practice, especially in applied or commercially driven projects. Also, evaluation metrics for RRI are also unclear, especially on how can researchers measure anticipation or reflexivity? (Ogoh et al., 2022)

Furthermore, RRI has been criticised for being too aligned with European policy contexts and sufficient attention is not paid to Global South epistemologies, indigenous knowledge systems, and institutional structural inequalities (Wakunuma et al., 2021). There are concerns regarding assumptions about who counts as a responsible actor, what constitutes legitimate knowledge, and how innovation should unfold often exclude Global South perspectives, Indigenous epistemologies, and non-Western worldviews. Another criticism is that RRI tends to focus on individual projects or researchers, rather than addressing structural drivers of irresponsibility in science and technology projects (Carrier and and Gartzlaff, 2020). Limited attention is paid to the political economy of innovation such as corporate influence, neoliberal funding regimes, or systemic inequities where there is a strong emphasis on consensus and soft governance over conflict resolution, advancing resistance, or transformative change. Without attention to power, inequality, and systemic drivers, RRI lacks the transformative drive needed in making innovation more acceptable beyond Europe.

Following the above review of literature, open questions that remained centered around how can African epistemologies and knowledge systems could be meaningfully included into the operationalisation of responsible research and innovation principles? Is there space within RRI frameworks to address the political economy of innovation, or do we need an entirely new paradigm to drive transformative and redistributive change? These are some of the questions the STRATEGIC project aims to explore and answer.

4. Methodology

This deliverable is informed by a combination of results from both primary and secondary research activities conducted in WP2 (Tasks 2.3) and WP3 (Tasks 3.3 and 3.4). This includes literature reviews conducted in Tasks 3.3 and as well as Focus Group discussions (Tasks 2.3) and Co-creation workshops (Tasks 3.4).

4.1. Literature Review

For the literature reviews, a mixture of narrative and systematic literature review was used. The central objective of Task 3.3 is to carry out a narrative literature review and analyse evidence concerning ethics for responsible design and deployment of digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa. It is also to check if ethical processes are envisaged regarding Responsible Innovation approaches to digital health technologies, in the context of clinical research and practice, highlighting differences across countries. Based on literature evidence, we also seek to identify strengths and weaknesses of existing Responsible Innovation approaches to digital health technologies in SSA. Databases used for sourcing data include PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Only papers published from 2014 till present and in English language were included for review. Key geographical delineation (SSA/Sub-Saharan Africa/Europe) was used. Search terms included:

*Ethics/ethics review process and digital health/digital technologies/digital technology and Responsible Innovation/responsible design/responsible deployment/responsible use and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice

*Ethics and mobile health/mHealth and Responsible Innovation/responsible design/responsible deployment/responsible use and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice

*Ethics and ICT and Responsible Innovation/responsible design/responsible deployment/responsible use and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice

* Responsible Research and Innovation/ Responsible Research and Innovation in Europe

* Responsible Research and Innovation in health/European healthcare/ Responsible adoption and deployment of technology/ Responsible adoption and deployment of health technology/ Responsible innovation/responsible design/responsible deployment/responsible adoption/responsible use

*Clinical research in Europe/clinical trials in Europe/ Health research/clinical practice

4.2. Focus groups and Co-Creation Workshop

Focus Groups (FGs) were carried out as part of Task 2.3 focused on identified values and principles that should shape responsible DHTs in Africa. Eight FGs have been carried out so far, the remaining two more to reach the target of ten FGs. Thirty-nine participants have so far participated in these FGs from about 15 countries in Europe and Africa. Participants were identified from the European & Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP) funded projects - both completed and ongoing. A list of names and contacts were collected from EDCTP projects as potential participants. Invitation emails were subsequently sent to them with a link to sign up for the available dates for the Focus Groups. Participants selected what dates to attend, which is voluntarily. The sessions were recorded in Teams, transcribed, and cleaned before coding and analysis. Thematic analysis using Nvivo 12 is currently ongoing. The initial findings are reported in section 6 of this deliverable.

The participants for the co-creation workshop were similarly identified using an email invitation with a link to sign up. Two out of four co-creation workshops have been conducted by diverse stakeholders from academia, industry, policy, and civic society. The workshop discussions are recorded in Teams, and initial thematic analysis is also ongoing. Sections 6, 7, and 8 are informed by these initial findings.

5. Existing responsible research and innovation approaches

5.1. ELSI and ELSA

ELSI (Ethical, Legal and Social Implications) and ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects) were important conceptual and programmatic frameworks in European science policy that preceded and informed some of the current approaches to research and innovation. ELSI originated in the United States with the Human Genome Project. These approaches emphasised early identification and mitigation of negative societal implications of science and technology. However, these were mainly reactive because issues were addressed after scientific progress was underway. Critics argued ELSI treated ethical, legal, and social issues as externalities to science rather than integral components of the research process.

ELSA became the European adaptation of ELSI, developed more fully during the Sixth (FP6) and Seventh (FP7) EU Framework Programme. This approach broadened the approach by aiming to integrate ELSA more upstream in research and development. It introduced more interdisciplinary approaches, involving social sciences, humanities, and ethics researchers in scientific projects.

5.2. EU Commission and UK Research Councils approach to RRI

The rise of RRI in Europe reflects a significant shift in science and technology governance, from managing risks and implications (as with ELSI/ELSA) to actively shaping innovation in line with societal values, needs, and expectations. RRI emerged as a normative and governance framework to ensure that research and innovation are socially desirable and ethically acceptable. Stakeholders, including the public, are actively involved in shaping research agendas. It draws from anticipatory governance (foresight, scenario planning, science and technology studies scholarship) and deliberative democracy and co-production.

Across the European Commission, RRI has been adopted as a new approach to science and innovation whereby all sectors and actors engaged can effectively make their perspective heard and nurtured. Across disciplines, RRI has lately gained prominence as a framework aimed at aligning scientific efforts with societal needs (von Schomberg 2012), encouraging the involvement of diverse stakeholders in addressing ethical and political issues (Ribeiro, Smith, and Millar 2017), and promoting industry engagement in solving wider social challenges (Lubberink et al. 2017; Schroeder and Kaplan 2019).

In addition to the European Commission, RRI has been adopted and integrated into the UK Engineering and Physical Science Research Council (EPSRC) research agenda. In the UK's EPSRC, the RRI AREA framework - Anticipate, Reflect, Engage, Act - rose to prominence within the UK EPSRC as a practical model for implementing responsible innovation, particularly in high-stakes emerging technologies like synthetic biology, artificial intelligence, and nanotechnology. It played a central role in translating RRI principles into research governance and is now considered a major UK contribution to the global discourse on responsible research and innovation.

There is growing international interest in fostering RRI through cross-regional collaboration, involving countries such as the United States, South Africa, and China (Chatfield et al. 2017). While RRI is a widely discussed topic within the Science and Technology Studies community in Europe, its application and adaptation in other regions remain relatively unexplored. Even with its

variations and adaptation, the current landscape of RRI has been largely shaped by the Global North, with limited consideration of how RRI or similar practices are understood and implemented in the Global South. As an area of research and practice, such literature explores the contextual factors that influence the development of responsible innovation practices and examine how these insights can support the creation of a globally relevant understanding of RRI. Insight from such spaces highlights that while certain activities in the Global South mirror those in the Global North, there are notable differences in terms of underlying motivations and organizational structures, thus foregrounding the need for an inclusive theoretical framework that acknowledges and incorporates cross-regional distinctions (Wakunuma et al., 2021). This is also emphasizing the need for critically examining RRI-like practices in the Global South to help contribute towards developing a culturally diverse understanding of RRI and one that fosters alignment between science and society while including often-overlooked stakeholders and approaches (Wakunuma et al., 2021).

5.3. Other design-led responsible innovation approaches in the global north

One of the most prominent responsible innovation model was established by the UK's Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT). This model reflects the UK government's growing recognition that science and innovation policy must align with democratic values, public trust, and ethical governance, especially considering emerging technologies like AI, quantum computing, and biotech. While the EPSRC's AREA framework operationalises RI at the research funding and practice level, the DSIT RI model represents a policy-level evolution, framing responsible innovation as central to national strategy, especially in a post-Brexit, global tech-competitive context. DSIT's model builds upon, but extends beyond, academic frameworks like AREA. It positions responsible innovation as a strategic capability for UK science and tech governance, with emphasis on trust and public legitimacy, inclusivity and diversity, and global leadership with dynamic governance and regulation.

From a largely design research perspective, approaches such as Responsibility-by-design, Ethics-by-design, and Value sensitive design have been developed and adopted as ways in which the diversity of perspective could inform the design and evaluation of digital technologies. Such approaches are meant as catalyst for ensuring the acceptability and desirability of research and innovation, even when highly contested across the literature.

5.3.1. Responsibility-by-Design

Responsibility-by-design is an approach that integrates ethical, social, and environmental considerations into the design and development process of technology and innovation, rather than treating them as add-ons or afterthoughts (Stahl et al., 2022). It is an evolution of the idea that responsibility is not just about outcomes, but about how technologies are conceived, built, and governed from the outset. In the context of technological innovation, responsibility-by-design provides a systemic approach to shaping technologies that are ethically aligned, socially responsive, **ecologically** sustainable, and politically inclusive.

5.3.2. Value-Sensitive Design

Value Sensitive Design (VSD) is a pioneering and widely influential approach to integrating human values into technology design. VSD aims to ensure that technologies reflect and support the moral and ethical values of individuals, communities, and societies (Friedman, 1996; Friedman et al., 2013). While responsibility-by-design focuses on embedding responsibility into the innovation process, VSD is more directly focused on embedding values (e.g. privacy, autonomy, justice, dignity) into the design of technology itself. VSD is a principled, theory-based, and iterative approach that combines empirical methods (like user research) with conceptual analysis (like philosophical inquiry) to uncover and integrate values from the start to the end of design. Some of the values identified in literature included privacy, autonomy, accessibility, justice and fairness, trust, dignity, sustainability and accountability. These values, as acknowledged by VSD, are not universal, highlighting the plurality of values across cultures and contexts, requiring value discovery and negotiation.

5.3.3. Ethics-By-Design

Ethics-by-Design (EbD) is a design and governance approach that aims to embed ethical principles, values, and norms directly into the architecture, code, and use-context of emerging technologies especially AI, algorithms, data systems, and digital infrastructures (Brey and Dainow, 2024). It shares many goals with value sensitive design and responsibility-by-design, but emphasises normative ethics more explicitly, often using principled frameworks to guide the technical design and development process. It draws from applied ethics (especially deontological, consequentialist, and virtue ethics), Computer and AI ethics, privacy-by-design and security-by-design **principles**, **and** shaped by RRI elements, particularly the "*Act*" and "*Anticipate*".

5.3.4. Limitation of Eurocentric design approaches

From the African perspectives, the above frameworks often uncritically assume universality of Western liberal values (e.g. autonomy, individual rights, transparency) while ignoring non-Western ontologies and moral systems. For example, RRI assumes a model of democratic deliberation and civic trust that doesn't easily map onto contexts where authority, kinship, and communal values dominate over liberal individualism. The risk is that of ethical imperialism, imposing Euro-American norms under the guise of "universal ethics". As pointed out in section 5.2, RRI and AREA promote procedural ethics (anticipate, engage, reflect), but often ignore deeper questions of political economy, global inequalities, and power asymmetries. These frameworks rarely interrogate who controls innovation, who benefits, and whose interests are protected, especially in postcolonial and extractive global contexts.

Additionally, the EU models are often premised on well-functioning institutions, civic infrastructures, and legal enforcement. However, these conditions are uneven or absent in many parts of the world. In essence, there is an assumption of institutional maturity and resource capacity that marginalises actors from the Global South or informal innovation spaces. These approaches are not easily translatable to structurally under-resourced or informally governed settings. Despite aspirations toward inclusivity, EU RRI practices tend to privilege institutional experts, scientists, and policymakers often excluding grassroots, indigenous, and marginalised communities. Engagements are frequently tokenistic, occurring late in the innovation process and driven by compliance rather than genuine co-creation.

For context, there has been the acknowledgement across design related discipline that open compound words such as Design, Research, and Design Innovation are ambiguous frames that necessitate considering the meaning(s) and association(s) inherited/relinquished when adopted across disciplinary contexts (Green and Lindley 2021). From the first and second wave of design research across Europe— a shift from design science to design studies - the question of moral judgement is central (Copper, 2019). In the first wave, the emphasis was on using scientific approaches to study design methods, whereas the second wave focuses attention on approaching design through its emerging terms beyond the prescription of the arts and the sciences. Consequently, the heterogeneity of 'Design' as a social and institutional practice brings with it the challenge of developing a consensus around the taxonomies of research and innovation, and how

such a discursive challenge could either widen/or narrow the application areas of ‘design’ as a distributed activity and process (Faste and Faste 2012).

Even with the multifaceted design-led research space of “design for, design by, design with, X-design and so on (Imbesi 2017), there remain prevailing issues associated with the ambiguities of terminologies such as “Responsibility, Value, and Community”, and their impact to practices across different communities of practices (Hernández et al., 2018; Tibbles et al, 2022). Even when well-intended, for example, often community centered social innovation co-opted the problem-solving paradox where social predicaments are to be identified and resolved designerly, mathematically, or computationally (Manzini, 2015). Here, community centered social innovation is conceived as a collection of ideas for/ or a collaborative process of re-organizing existing social capabilities in ways that bring about incremental or radical social change. As a result of this rhetorical framing of institutional issues in Europe along the line of “design for, by, with,” structural predicaments such as social inequality, power imbalance, and economic injustice are reduced to design problem formulation and technological solution optimization

Against techno-solutionism of community design, Cangiano, Romano, and Loglio (2017) emphasize the need for open approaches to Design where equitable social values and ethical principles ought to inform the adoption and scaling of social innovation projects across Europe. More recently, Mattew et al. (2022) examined the notion of design for the public as an open approach to Design where the convergence/divergence of interest within the Australian context necessitates a reformulation of the design community of research and practice. From such an outlook, one might recognize how the conception of the Design enterprise as an “infrastructuring” and “institutioning” mechanism for societal change and impact might support aligning competing public and design interests (Unteidig et al. 2017).

With the complex nature of social issues such as inequality and injustice, designer researchers and practitioners were tasked with developing social interventions that could mitigate or minimize those predicaments – thus the framing of innovation across the lines of human values, wider communities, social ethics and so on. However, the emphasis on approaches such as Responsibility-by-design and Value sensitive design focuses attention on methods, processes, and outcomes over long-standing issues around the values that implicate the enterprise of design as

ethics and politics (Unteidig, et al. 2017). Furthermore, Ethics-by-Design rely on abstract, often decontextualised principles (e.g. fairness, privacy), without engaging with how values are culturally constructed and contested. In pluralistic societies, values are not only multiple, but there are often tensions. This is something the EU frameworks typically sidestep.

As widely recognized by the Design community, Design in the broadest sense is rendered as a precursor or a compositional instrument for societal changes e.g., the Bauhaus movement. Even when the discipline and profession of Design places the public good central to digital social innovation (Berman 2008; Mathew et al. 2022), social innovation discourses tend to focus on how aesthetically/materially relevant a design artefact or intervention is to common societal need, or what are the suitable features of social innovation in relation to their material function within existing structures of society (Unteidig, et al. 2017). One might notice the emphasis on how to design (method) and what to design (outcome) for societal change, and not why we design (value) or for whom we design (ethics).

For Matthew and colleagues (2022, 5-6), “Design does not, nor cannot, ‘solve’ social problems; but it can and does shape the complex topographies around such issues in various ways. Design necessarily participates in shaping the material and systemic landscape in which social problems emerge and are recognized as predicaments for particular publics. Yet, how the discipline of design ought to respond to these circumstances of its activity remain open question, particularly as it is often the case that design's role in the identification of issues and matters of concern do not visibly emerge until design proposals have been developed and consequences can be anticipated—or worse, until after wide-scale deployment when consequences are only too apparent. This in turn often feeds more demand for additional design 'solutions' to be created and deployed in response to such consequences”. Therefore, in the remainder of this section, we provide an overview of some of the approaches widely adopted across African landscape and then assess the extent to which those approaches and frameworks could inform the design and adoption of digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa.

5.4. Common approaches in Africa

With specific emphasis on the global south, the influence of local institutions, cultural traditions, and contextual factors on designing effective responsible innovation remains an open area of inquiry. Different countries and regions offer distinct environments and conditions for

implementing responsible innovation. In the Global North, RRI tends to be grounded in Western scientific knowledge, with a focus on technological and product-based solutions aimed at tackling large-scale societal issues. In contrast, RRI practices in the Global South often emphasize collaborative knowledge production where indigenous knowledge has a vital role (Jauhiainen and Hooli 2017; Torri and Laplante 2009). As a result, innovation in these contexts also encompasses new social practices, institutional forms, designs, and technologies that respond directly to local needs, often shaped by experiences of inequality and social exclusion.

In rural areas, local communities often play a crucial role in guiding responsible innovation, including choices about whether to pursue innovation and which technologies or practices to adopt (Valkenburg et al. 2019). Nevertheless, the Global South is far from uniform; it encompasses significant contextual diversity both between and within regions. Hence, rethinking RRI must begin by carefully examining the core differences in the contextual and structural dimensions of RRI practices in the Global North and South. This understanding is essential for developing a comprehensive and inclusive global RRI framework.

In the context of SSA, Malawi (as reported by the UNESCO Global Observatory of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy Instruments (GO-SPIN)) provides an example of Global South perspective. With Malawi as one of the least developed countries in Africa, it exemplifies many traits typical of developing economies in the Global South. The country has long grappled with economic difficulties, and its innovation efforts have been hindered by weak governance, political corruption, and widespread illiteracy. These challenges have significantly affected the country's capacity for research and innovation. Additionally, cultural factors such as ethnic tensions further obstruct the formation of a unified innovation strategy. The limited number of researchers in Malawi highlights the lack of a clear human resources strategy in science and engineering, contributing to low research and innovation output.

Furthermore, RRI has gained traction in the Global North and in parts of North Africa like Morocco and Egypt but remains largely overlooked in Sub-Saharan Africa. The model promoted by the European Commission, since 2011, doesn't adequately tackle the specific challenges of the Global South. Unlike the North's top-down approach where governments dictate RRI goals to researchers and practitioners, the Upanzi Network launched in 2021 as an African collaboration of engineering research labs including Carnegie Mellon University Africa and partners in Morocco, Botswana, and South Africa. The network was supported by the Gates Foundation, adopting a

bottom-up implementation strategy where users define their needs by guiding developers and researchers in design and implementation of digital innovation (Maenner, 2024).

Nevertheless, ongoing governance reforms are opening new avenues for advancing research and innovation. Such efforts, in term of policy reform, now aim to protect indigenous knowledge, and increasing emphasis is being placed on engaging local communities and incorporating traditional knowledge practices into innovation processes. Core elements of RRI such as democratic participation, inclusive governance, and stakeholder engagement are gradually emerging within Malawi's research and innovation landscape.

For example, Hartley et al. (2019) highlight the role of Responsible Innovation in guiding low-tech innovation toward tackling global challenges in the Global South. The authors illustrated how RRI provides a framework for structured dialogue, foresight, and stakeholder involvement. Similarly, emerging Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) strategies across the region, including Malawi's policy reforms, reflect RRI-related thinking and are beginning to shape policy development (Manyuchi and Mugabe, 2018). In such spaces, socially driven innovation practices such as community participation, indigenous knowledge exchange, social impact efforts, and stakeholder collaboration are central to innovation processes. These approaches are especially important in contexts marked by limited regulation, low public awareness, and the marginalization of vulnerable populations. Empowering communities to contribute their knowledge is key to enabling meaningful and sustainable innovation. A defining feature of RRI-like approaches in the Global South, therefore, is their emphasis on community-based models and grassroots participation, which are essential for realizing tangible local benefits (Wakunuma et al., 2021). In the context of the Global South, the literature identifies two key approaches to RRI: capital-oriented and livelihood-oriented.

5.4.1. Capital-oriented approach

The *capital-oriented approach* typically follows a structured, formal, and top-down mode led by both private investment and public funding. These strategies are aimed at generating technological advancements and scientific knowledge, often targeting large-scale urban, national, or global

challenges. Such models emphasize collaboration among key stakeholders, such as policymakers, academic institutions, and industry, and often seek to include civil society as a representative of the broader public.

However, these efforts tend to overlook rural and grassroots perspectives, possibly due to an overarching focus on including civil society. Yet, civil society is a broad category that can encompass interest groups that do not necessarily reflect the views or needs of the general population, particularly marginalized or underrepresented communities. Rainey, Wakunuma, and Stahl (2017) point out that there is a lack of clarity about what constitutes civil society organizations (CSOs), which can undermine their effectiveness in research and innovation processes. Consequently, instead of promoting inclusivity, the capital-oriented model of RRI may unintentionally exclude certain social groups. In practice, RRI in the Global North is largely shaped and directed by policymakers, who also tend to be its primary funders.

5.4.2. Livelihood-oriented approach

The livelihood-oriented approach is typically rooted in local contexts, informal in nature, and follows bottom-up strategies led by grassroots and non-profit organizations and supported by inclusive policy frameworks. It focuses on co-producing social innovations and transdisciplinary knowledge, particularly in response to context specific challenges. This form of RRI is often shaped by marginalized groups, such as community associations, cooperatives, and citizen collectives, who invite external collaborators to work with them toward sustainable outcomes.

Due to its informal structure, this type of RRI offers greater flexibility for community groups, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and civil society organizations (CSOs) to adapt the RRI agenda to meet specific local needs. Policymakers and academia are scarcely involved in promoting RRI in the Global South. Institutional weaknesses and a lack of political commitment make it difficult to enact strong RRI policies, which inevitably weakens academic implementation. Additionally, public research funding is often too limited to support ethically driven, technology-focused RRI efforts.

Across communities in SSA, publicly funded RRI programs and policies emphasizing socio-ethical considerations are either minimal or completely missing. Countries like Malawi, for instance, are heavily reliant on international aid and priorities are skewed toward addressing immediate needs—basic survival and livelihoods—rather than adopting socio-ethical RRI frameworks. RRI efforts tend to emerge from local communities and civil society organizations dedicated to national development, while government bodies largely avoid engaging in policy-level efforts to foster socio-ethical RRI. According to literature findings, it is essential to broaden the RRI conversation to include informal, grassroots approaches. Evidently, community-based practices offer valuable models that deserve recognition within the RRI landscape, and RRI practitioners should incorporate this knowledge into their frameworks (Wakunuma et al., 2021).

5.4.3. Layered approach in sub-Saharan Africa

It is common knowledge across sectors that researchers and innovators should integrate ethical principles and strategies into their everyday processes and practices to assess the practical applicability of their projects and products. Much like the well-established “security-by-design” approach where security considerations are built in from the outset, RRI has been adopted across SSA to promote an “ethics-by-design” methodology. In such cases, communities proactively evaluate how their creations might affect individuals and society, ensuring adherence to core principles such as privacy, security, and gender equality, etc. To ensure accountability in sub-Saharan Africa, for example, Upanzi Network developed a *layered RRI framework* that emphasises:

- 1) privacy and security, benefits to society, public engagement, ethics and governance;
- 2) responsiveness, transparency and accountability, fairness, gender equality and inclusivity;
- 3) human agency and oversight. This framework of RRI principles enables developers to demonstrate to stakeholders how their work positively impacts society.

A key objective of Upanzi Network is to shape technology policy recommendations that support low- and middle-income countries. As reported by Maenner (2024), the Upanzi Network envisaged goals are:

- 1) Build, experiment with, and contribute back to existing open standard digital technologies for the public good, and demonstrate technological solutions that can provide beneficial, cost-effective and interoperable digital services for Africans;
- 2) Implement secure, privacy-protecting, fair, resilient and trustworthy digital technologies;
- 3) Enable a more inclusive digital technology environment through the development of digital services that are well-suitable to resource-constrained individuals and environments;
- 4) Empower users of digital technologies by building and promoting the development of human-centered digital solutions;
- 5) Build a network of existing African academic institutions that will act as trusted players where decision makers get trustworthy guidance about different technological solutions (Maenner, 2024).

5.4.4. Emerging approaches in sub-Saharan Africa – AI design and adoption

In sub-Saharan Africa, the growth of artificial intelligence has been uneven, while pockets of innovation thrive, many regions are lagging behind. Literature findings highlight an urgent need for African innovators, policymakers, civil society groups, and academic institutions to significantly increase their involvement in AI development (Oxford Insights and the International Development Research Centre, 2020). It is vital for Africans to lead in developing AI technologies that account for the continent’s socio-economic and infrastructural realities. Deploying AI tools without proper adaptation can cause prolonged harm, undermining human rights, failing to tackle Africa-specific challenges, and wasting precious resources. Such missteps risk eroding government confidence and stalling AI investment. To avoid these pitfalls, the creation of a responsible AI ecosystem is essential, one that empowers local researchers and innovators. Responsible AI “focuses on ensuring the ethical, transparent and accountable use of AI technologies in a manner consistent with user expectations, organisational values and societal laws and norms” (Gwagwa et al., 2021).

Consequently, AI policies grounded in the principles of responsibility and inclusivity offer numerous advantages, such as addressing inequalities, preserving cultural values, promoting diversity, and enhancing the effectiveness of AI-driven solutions. For these reasons, a strong and

consistent commitment to responsible AI should be a top priority for developers, policymakers, researchers, and funding bodies alike.

For example, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) needs assessment claims that future initiatives must tackle key cross-cutting areas, including education, skill development, research and development, data governance, and the elimination of gender bias and discrimination in AI creation and usage. Major global tech companies have acknowledged the importance of directing investments into Africa and ensuring that infrastructure development includes the active participation of Africans. Nevertheless, interdisciplinary collaboration remains limited—for instance, computer science departments in many African universities rarely engage with other academic disciplines, a challenge less common in European institutions. Most African computer science departments are still working toward building such cross-disciplinary connections. An exception is South Africa’s Centre for Artificial Intelligence Research (CAIR), a significant national program launched in 2011 to strengthen AI capabilities. CAIR connects nine research groups across six universities: the University of Cape Town, University of KwaZulu-Natal, North-West University, University of Pretoria, Stellenbosch University, and the University of the Western Cape. These efforts reflect South Africa’s commitment to establishing the institutional foundations necessary to shape AI policy and support its broader implementation within the country (UNESCO, 2017).

According to literature findings, developing and deploying AI responsibly in Africa requires tackling a range of complex, interconnected challenges within the broader AI landscape. These include the future of work, environmental sustainability, algorithmic bias, the inclusion of marginalized communities, and concerns around digital or algorithmic colonialism. In the context of current challenges, two critical issues should be considered: risks of AI technologies jeopardizing human rights, and risks related to AI, gender and inclusion (Gwagwa et al.,2021):

- 1) *Risks of AI technologies jeopardizing human rights*: With China increasingly exporting dual-use AI technologies to Africa, concerns have emerged that these tools could be employed for widespread surveillance targeting specific social groups—such as ethnic minorities, historically marginalized communities, or individuals viewed as political threats. While the actual extent of such practices remains uncertain and requires further investigation, a recent report indicates that countries like South Africa, Nigeria, Kenya, Uganda, and Zimbabwe are already integrating AI with data collection technologies to

consolidate sensitive population data. This data is intended to improve access to essential public services. Globally, there is growing advocacy for the development of responsible governance models to guide the ethical use of AI and related technologies—particularly in ways that promote social empowerment. This includes encouraging collaboration with civil society organizations, digital rights advocates, and young innovators across Africa to build accountability frameworks that align with the ethical and democratic needs of the continent. The United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights has also issued recommendations for embedding human rights considerations into AI development. These include conducting human rights impact assessments and adopting policies designed to prevent AI-driven violations of fundamental rights (United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner, 2018).

- 2) *Risks related to AI, gender and inclusion*: Gender inequality - alongside other forms of multidimensional inequality - continues to be a deeply rooted issue affecting women in many parts of sub-Saharan Africa. However, some progress is being made. In countries such as Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, emerging AI start-up ecosystems are beginning to support the inclusion and advancement of women. Additionally, countries like Ghana and Rwanda are implementing forward-looking policies to boost female participation in computer science, with backing from major tech companies. Several initiatives are specifically designed to involve young people and girls. For instance, South Africa has introduced coding into school curricula, while Ghana is promoting information and communication technology (ICT) and coding programs aimed at girls. Code4CapeTown in South Africa is one notable example, investing in training female coders and running coding programs for high school girls. At the same time, advocates for gender-inclusive AI are drawing attention to the biases embedded in data and algorithms, particularly how these systems often disadvantage non-white women (Gwagwa et al.,2021).

The literature stresses that If AI technologies are not developed and implemented in a fair and ethical way, there is a real risk that they will deepen existing inequalities, both across Africa and globally (Smith, Neupan, 2018). While African countries are highly diverse, they also share key similarities, such as common historical experiences and cultural values, which create opportunities for collaboration in establishing ethical governance frameworks that reflect shared principles. Governments have a vital role to play in fostering a responsible AI ecosystem. It will be important not only using AI to create digital solutions tailored to Africa’s longstanding challenges, but also

to critically evaluate and envisage how these technologies may impact inclusion, human rights, and cultural integrity (Smith, Neupan, 2018).

5.4.5. Emerging approaches in sub-Saharan Africa – AI ethics and governance

There is a growing concern in academic literature that current discussions around AI ethics and governance often overlook or exclude African perspectives (Eke & Ogoh, 2022). This has led to mounting warnings about a possible "digital" or "algorithmic" colonization of Africa, due to the absence of African cultural values and ethical frameworks in global AI ethics debates (Adams, 2021; Birhane, 2023; Mohamed & Isaac, 2020). In response, an increasing number of scholars are calling for the inclusion of distinctly African ethical traditions in AI development, with many emphasizing the importance of indigenous systems such as Ubuntu and communality to help fill this gap. At the same time, several African countries and regional bodies are beginning to establish their own AI governance frameworks, often through the creation of national or continental AI strategies (AI Blueprint, 2021; AU AI Strategy, 2024; Benin, 2023; Ghana, 2022; Mauritius, 2018; Rwanda, 2023; Senegal, 2023; Sierra Leone, 2023).

In the literature, Ubuntu is widely recognized as a pan-African ethical system with well-defined normative principles that could effectively guide AI ethics. However, there is evidence that, with the exception of Benin's AI Strategy, neither national nor continental AI strategies explicitly incorporate a distinctly African ethical viewpoint on AI. Even in Benin's case, Ubuntu is only indirectly referenced, without any detailed explanation of how it relates specifically to AI (Yilma, 2025). Although recent reports indicate that thirteen African countries have adopted AI strategies, the majority of these documents are not publicly accessible (UNESCO Survey, 2021: 22). National AI strategies—or AI policies—are important tools that outline a government's priorities, objectives, and policy directions for maximizing the benefits and managing the risks of AI, including ethical concerns. When such a strategy is adopted at the continental level, as in the case of the African Union, the aim is to foster a unified approach to AI across member states. Therefore, AI strategies are critical for identifying and embedding local or indigenous ethical perspectives within AI governance.

A significant number of AI initiatives are being led by actors from regions commonly referred to as the "Global North," primarily composed of Western countries. This has prompted a growing body of literature that critiques "Western AI ethics", namely, ethical frameworks promoted by

Western institutions, such as the OECD Recommendation on Artificial Intelligence (OECD/LEGAL/0449, May 2019, amended November 2023). Perplexities have been raised not only about how AI systems are designed, developed, and implemented, but also about how they are governed through ethical guidelines that reflect Western priorities.

Since much of AI research and development is concentrated in the West and carried out by Western developers, ethical perspectives and values from the Global South - particularly African perspectives - are often overlooked (Hassan, 2023). AI technologies are frequently built upon values central to Western societies, such as individual autonomy (Mhlambi & Tiribelli, 2023). This exclusion of African ethics and knowledge systems from AI ethics debates has been described as a form of “epistemic injustice.”

Originally introduced by Fricker, epistemic injustice includes two key forms: testimonial and hermeneutical. Testimonial injustice occurs when someone’s knowledge or credibility is devalued due to their identity or social status (Fricker, 2007: 9–14). In the context of AI, disregarding non-Western ethical systems and knowledge in both AI development and governance reflects this form of injustice. Hermeneutical injustice refers to the systemic and structural limitations that prevent certain social groups from fully contributing to the generation and interpretation of knowledge. This also applies in AI when these groups lack access to or recognition within the frameworks that shape the development of technology and its ethical oversight (Yilma, 2025).

One of the clearest examples of hermeneutical injustice in AI ethics is the exclusion of voices from global AI conversations. Literature findings increasingly caution that this form of epistemic injustice could result in “digital colonization” of the African continent. Also referred to as “ethical colonialism,” this occurs when AI development is guided solely by Anglo-European moral philosophies that prioritize rational, autonomous individuals. The outcome is the continued marginalization of people in the Global South—particularly in Africa—by creating technologies that ignore or misrepresent their values and contexts. In response, African scholars often point to Ubuntu—a relational ethical framework rooted in African philosophy—as a way to address this imbalance. Ubuntu emphasizes that personhood is not an individual achievement, but something developed through positive, communal relationships. Under this view, individuals become fully realized persons through their connections with others, placing the community at the center of

ethical life. This approach clashes with Western philosophical traditions, which generally stress individual autonomy, rational thinking, and prudence as essential for achieving a good life. While Western ethics tend to be rights-based, Ubuntu relies more on duties and responsibilities within the community, highlighting its communitarian nature.

A notable articulation of Ubuntu can be found in a 2021 Resolution by the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, a key intergovernmental human rights body in Africa. In this resolution, the Commission urged member states of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights to incorporate African values, ethics, and norms into the development of AI governance frameworks, as a way to address epistemic injustice (Resolution 473, 2021: Preamble, Paragraph 2). The resolution highlights specific elements of indigenous African ethics, including Ubuntu, a communitarian ethos, resistance to domination, and protection against racial and other forms of discrimination (Paragraph 19).

The Resolution's footnote defines Ubuntu as "the shared humanity that connects all of us to each other" (footnote 3). While Ubuntu is not directly referenced in UNESCO's 2021 Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence, the values it promotes are closely aligned with those emphasized by the African Human Rights Commission. For example, the UNESCO document advocates for peaceful, just, and interconnected societies, highlighting solidarity, human interdependence, and harmony with the natural world (Paragraphs 22–23). This alignment is particularly notable given that six of the 24 experts involved in drafting the UNESCO Recommendation were from Africa.

As shown by the extensive body of work on value-sensitive design (VSD), technology can be intentionally developed to reflect specific values across various sectors, including healthcare (Umbrello et al., 2021). In fact, the central argument behind claims of epistemic injustice in AI ethics stems from the dominance of Western values in shaping AI design. However, the effectiveness of VSD depends on the clarity and specificity of the values being applied, so they can be meaningfully integrated into technology. This poses a challenge in the case of Ubuntu, whose broad and generalized meaning may make it difficult to translate into concrete principles for AI design or governance frameworks.

The question of what defines African values or ethics remains widely debated and unresolved within academic literature. Given the continent’s immense cultural and linguistic diversity, it is likely that Africa encompasses a broad range of ethical systems or “moral perspectives” that could inform AI governance. One practical way to explore whether such national or pan-African ethical principles exist is to analyze the content of national and continental AI policy documents: Mauritius was the first African nation to adopt a national AI strategy (Mauritius AI Strategy, 2018). Unlike other strategies, Mauritius’s approach primarily emphasizes the economic and social advantages of AI, with minimal attention to ethical concerns. Apart from a brief mention of the need for a “clear, explicit and transparent code of ethics” outlining permissible uses of AI, the strategy does not present an ethical framework, nor does it specify who should create this code or when it should be implemented.

For example, the nation of Ghana, the first West African country to launch a national AI strategy (Ghana AI Strategy, 2022), addresses ethics under Pillar 4, which focuses on “data access and governance.” However, rather than proposing a distinctly Ghanaian or African ethical model, the strategy stresses the importance of promoting guidance on ethical, safe, trustworthy, and secure AI practices for developers and users (Ghana AI Strategy, 2022: pp. 17, 22, 32). The Ghana AI Strategy (2022) refers to international ethical frameworks, specifically those by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), as the key guidelines to be reviewed and shared (pp. 32–33). This indicates that the strategy not only avoids developing or promoting a context-specific ethical framework but also neglects to consider indigenous African values.

Furthermore, Benin is the most recent sub-Saharan African country to publish a national AI strategy (Benin AI Strategy, 2023). While the document places strong emphasis on AI's potential to support development, it also recognizes the importance of addressing ethical and accountability concerns through suitable legal and regulatory structures (Strategic Objectives 1–4). Two important aspects of Benin’s ethical approach to AI deserve attention. First, the strategy appears to view the safeguarding of fundamental human rights—especially data protection—as the primary, if not the only, ethical issue (p. 47). However, this seemingly limited focus is expanded when the strategy outlines what should be included in the future ethical framework. This more detailed specification marks the second key point. (Benin AI Strategy, 2023: p. 35):

“This legislation should, for example, formalise and institute impact analyses and monitoring of AI solutions throughout their lifecycle [...]. Any such monitoring must be instituted to ensure that AI systems are designed and implemented with due consideration for key concepts such as people, the planet, prosperity, peace, transparency, justice and fairness, accountability, non-maleficence, privacy, benevolence [...] and solidarity”.

However, the Strategy does not provide details on how these concepts will be translated into practical, action-oriented principles. Rwanda is the most recent country to implement a national AI policy (Rwanda AI Policy, 2023). Among its six key focus areas is “Practical Ethical Guidelines,” where the government commits to developing and widely disseminating clear and actionable guidelines for the ethical development and deployment of AI (Rwanda AI Policy, 2023: 2, 4–5, 18). Neither the Policy nor the forthcoming guidelines seem intended to establish a distinctly “African” perspective on AI ethics.

Regarding continental AI policy, the African Union (AU) Continental AI Strategy acknowledges risks to “African and pan-African values” posed by AI (AU Continental AI Strategy, 2024: 25–26). One strategic goal for 2030 is to develop AI ethics guidelines tailored to the African context (AU Continental AI Strategy, 2024: 28–29, 35), which could imply drawing on indigenous ethics and values. The Strategy emphasizes that these guidelines should “respect” African culture and values (AU Continental AI Strategy, 2024: 29). Additionally, it specifies that the guidelines should honour values like Ubuntu, which prioritizes community over individuality (AU Continental AI Strategy, 2024: 4–5). However, the Strategy tends to see AI as a threat to African values rather than incorporating these values into defining AI ethics. By not clarifying how AI ethics should be understood or shaped in an African context, the Strategy does not make a significant contribution to establishing a shared African viewpoint on AI ethics.

Another continental initiative is the AI for Africa Blueprint, which is supported by the German government and led by South Africa. It was created by a working group composed of members from various African sectors (AI Blueprint, 2021: 14). The Blueprint’s main goal is to help establish a unified African stance on AI by offering a framework for African governments to develop their national AI strategies (AI Blueprint, 2021: 23–25). While it emphasizes including an AI ethical framework in national strategies and suggests creating a regional AI policy body, the

Blueprint does not clearly define ethical principles that reflect a shared African perspective on AI ethics (AI Blueprint, 2021: 17, 44). Moreover, the national strategies mentioned earlier do not explicitly state that they used the Blueprint as a guide, though Ghana’s AI Strategy seems to have heavily relied on it. A key concern with this method of developing AI governance tools is that ethical issues might be overlooked. Teams that include multidisciplinary experts, especially those with expertise in ethics, are more likely to address AI ethics meaningfully. This may partly explain why AI ethics receives limited focus in many African AI strategies.

Some stances in the literature suggest that neither the normative framework of Ubuntu nor the current AI governance initiatives provide a clear, consistent, and practical framework for an “African AI ethics.” According to these stances, references to Ubuntu or “African” ethics are rarely found or implied in recent national or continental AI governance efforts. There is a growing call among African stakeholders to clearly define what “African ethics” means—specifically, to identify distinct and indigenous ethical values or principles that are relevant to AI and unique to African communities, while explaining how these principles can be applied in the development and governance of AI technologies (Yilma, 2025).

From our initial findings, an African approach to responsible innovation should be context-specific, value-plural, participatory, and grounded in African epistemologies and sociopolitical realities. We found that such an approach must appreciate Africa’s value Pluralism and relational Ethics, moving beyond individualist ethics (e.g. privacy, autonomy) to include relational values like *ubuntu*, *communal responsibility*, *intergenerational justice*, and *relational autonomy*. For instance, ubuntu’s emphasis on “*a person is a person through other persons*” challenges Western liberal autonomy. Another insight from the findings is the recognise that ethical and innovation frameworks are not neutral but often carry colonial or imperial logics. Centering indigenous knowledge systems, local problem framings, and communal narratives as valid epistemic resources are critical. Designing innovations that respond to local material conditions, infrastructure constraints, and social realities (e.g. informal economies, plural legal systems, oral cultures). As regards deliberative and participatory approaches, leverage community-based innovation models. Traditional councils, elders, youth groups, cooperatives, and faith-based organisations in decision-making are of critical importance. This includes expanding stakeholder models to include non-expert, grassroots voices and avoid technocratic dominance.

6. Emerging Responsible Research and Innovation Approaches for Africa

Initial findings from our research point to the need for a distinctively African approach to responsible innovation, one that goes beyond adapting existing European frameworks and instead is rooted in Africa's diverse epistemologies, moral worldviews, and socio-political realities. Rather than applying a one-size-fits-all model, our participants stressed that responsible innovation in Africa must be context-specific, value-plural, relational, and participatory. This approach recognises that innovation does not occur in a vacuum but is shaped by, and must be responsive to, the lived experiences, values, and aspirations of local communities.

A key theme that emerged is the need to move beyond dominant Western ethical frameworks, which often emphasise individualistic values such as autonomy, informed consent, and data privacy. While important, these values do not sufficiently capture the relational ethics embedded in many African moral and social systems. Participants consistently highlighted Ubuntu philosophy which posits that “a person is a person through other persons” as foundational to a responsible African innovation approach. Ubuntu challenges Western notions of the self as autonomous and independent, instead promoting communal responsibility, care, reciprocity, and intergenerational justice. Values such as relational autonomy, collective accountability, and social harmony are essential ethical anchors that should shape how innovation is conceptualised, governed, and practiced in African contexts.

Importantly, the findings also highlight that ethical and innovation frameworks are never culturally or politically neutral. Many participants noted that dominant global models of research ethics and innovation governance often carry colonial, imperial, or technocratic logics. As a result, the uptake of these models in African settings can reproduce epistemic injustice by marginalising local knowledge systems and community-based traditions. There is a pressing need to centre African epistemologies, including indigenous philosophies, oral traditions, and communal problem-solving practices, not as supplementary but as legitimate and primary sources of knowledge. This involves validating local problem framings, material conditions, and innovation needs such as those related to informal economies, plural legal systems, and infrastructure constraints. In short,

responsible innovation must respond to the realities on the ground, not abstract or universalised models.

Participants also pointed to the importance of community-led participatory innovation processes, drawing on traditional councils, elders, youth groups, cooperatives, women's associations, and faith-based organisations as trusted and culturally embedded institutions for collective decision-making. These actors have long histories of navigating moral dilemmas, resolving conflict, and fostering inclusive governance. As such, they offer rich resources for innovation ethics and governance. Incorporating such voices also challenges the technocratic bias of dominant stakeholder models, which often privilege expert or institutional actors while overlooking the insights of so-called "non-experts" and grassroots actors. A genuinely responsible approach must therefore expand the stakeholder landscape, embedding deliberation and co-creation at all stages of the innovation cycle.

Finally, the findings underscore the importance of aligning responsible innovation in Africa with digital sovereignty, data justice, and fair benefit sharing. Participants expressed concern over the extractive data practices associated with some global research and innovation partnerships, where data is collected in African contexts but analysed, stored, and monetised elsewhere. This will mean preventing extractive data practices and dependency on foreign infrastructure, and that any responsible innovation model for Africa should have decoloniality as its central objective. Such practices risk perpetuating new forms of digital dependency and neo-colonialism. A future-oriented African model must ensure that data infrastructures, governance mechanisms, and benefits remain under local control, aligned with national and regional development priorities. This includes building local capacities in digital infrastructure, safeguarding community consent, and ensuring equitable sharing of research and innovation outcomes.

Taken together, these insights suggest that decoloniality must be the central organising principle of any responsible innovation model for Africa. Decolonization here is not merely adjusting existing models to fit the computational abstraction of realities, but rather continuously reimagining innovation from within African traditions and conditions of living. The decoloniality

called into question requires focused attention to power imbalances, historical injustice, and epistemic diversity, while fostering ethical creativity rooted in African experiences. In doing so, Africa does not just adapt to global RRI discourses, it actively contributes a transformative vision of responsible innovation that prioritises justice, relationality, and collective flourishing.

7. Focusing on Decoloniality in Responsible Research and Innovation

Building on emerging insights from the series of participatory research activities carried out to date, we recognise that the STRATEGIC approach to responsible innovation will have a special focus on continual decoloniality. Focusing on decoloniality in responsible innovation requires confronting the deep historical and structural imbalances that continue to shape how knowledge, technology, and capital are produced, governed, and distributed globally. While mainstream RI frameworks in Europe have advanced the integration of ethics, inclusion, and public engagement into science and innovation, they often remain anchored in Eurocentric epistemologies and institutional logics. Decoloniality urges us to move beyond merely diversifying stakeholders or values within existing structures and instead to interrogate and transform the colonial foundations of the global innovation system including who gets to define problems, who is recognised as a knower, and whose futures are prioritised.

A decolonial approach to RI therefore shifts focus from technocratic and procedural notions of responsibility to epistemic justice, digital sovereignty, and relational accountability. It recognises that colonial legacies continue to manifest through extractive research practices, data colonialism, and the imposition of universal ethical frameworks that ignore local worldviews. Decolonial RI demands a reorientation of innovation toward the lived realities, knowledge systems, and contextual priorities of formerly colonised communities. This includes valuing indigenous technologies, oral traditions, communal ethics (such as *ubuntu*), and alternative ontologies that challenge the dominance of rationalist, individualist, and utilitarian paradigms.

Critically, decoloniality in RI is not simply about inclusion within Western-defined spaces of innovation, but about redesigning those spaces altogether. This is an extension of long-standing question around the future of Africa as a knowledge economy where the African narrative of innovation is problematised within (and without) the Western syntax of historization. Such

intellectual exercises draw upon earlier decolonial traditions of African studies where those of the Africana doctrine like Charles Mills and Frantz Fanon seek to construct African discourse from within modernist traditions as a way of reinvention from within, whereas those of the African stand like Kwasi Wiredu and Ngugi Wa Thiong'o' have advocated for developing decolonial narratives outside Western epistemological orders (Mitova, 2020). Building on both intellectual positions, we recognise that a decolonialised RI requires building pluriversal systems of knowledge production and governance, where African philosophies are not peripheral but foundational. This might involve rethinking data governance to prioritise collective sovereignty and creating funding stream and evaluation frameworks that support context-specific research practices. The goal is not to "catch up" with dominant models of innovation, but to reimagine innovation itself as a space for resistance, regeneration, and liberation.

Ultimately, focusing on decoloniality in RI is a political, ethical, and epistemic imperative. It pushes beyond the limitations of procedural ethics and toward a transformative vision of responsibility that is rooted in diverse histories and plural futures. Such an approach acknowledges that innovation is never neutral, and that to be truly responsible, it must reckon with the unequal past, confront existing inequalities, and amplify the agency and knowledge of those long marginalised by global science and technology systems.

8. Future Directions

In providing a preview of RRI across the Global North, we identified specific open-ended question around its adaptation across African context and communities. These questions touched upon how African epistemologies and knowledge systems could be meaningfully included into the operationalization of responsible research and innovation principles? Or more so, exploring whether there is a need for an entirely new paradigm to drive transformative and redistributive change across the wider healthcare ecosystem in African. As part of the STRATEGIC project, a series of participatory research activities including semi-structured interviews, use case analysis, focus group discussions (on-going), and co-creation workshops (ongoing) have been conducted across multiple African contexts. These activities were intentionally designed to elicit local experiences, ethical priorities, values and principles, and practical insights from diverse stakeholders involved in the development and use of Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) in clinical research and trials. Stakeholders engaged in this process include researchers, regulators,

healthcare workers, trial participants, community representatives, ethicists, and policymakers.

The objective of these engagements has been to move beyond normative assumptions imported from Global North contexts and instead support the co-creation of an African-aligned framework for responsible innovation. This emerging framework is rooted in the ethical, social, and epistemic realities of African societies and seeks to respond to specific challenges and opportunities posed by digital health technologies (DHT) in clinical settings such as issues of digital access, informed consent, expanded trust, data sovereignty, and benefit sharing.

Looking ahead, the next phase of the STRATEGIC project will focus on testing and validating this co-created framework in real-world clinical research settings. This validation process will ensure the framework is practical, context-sensitive, and capable of guiding ethical innovation and governance in diverse African environments. Through this iterative process, we aim to refine the framework to ensure it is usable by both researchers and regulators across varied national and institutional contexts.

Ultimately, the STRATEGIC project will develop a set of evidence-based recommendations for National Ethics Committees (NECs) and National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs) in Africa (WP4). These recommendations will be tailored to support ethical review, innovation governance, and policy formulation around the use of DHTs in research. In addition, the project will produce a series of training modules and capacity-building programmes for relevant stakeholders including researchers, regulators, ethics committee members, and community advisory boards (WP5). These training efforts will ensure that the responsible innovation principles embedded in the framework can be widely disseminated, adopted, and institutionalised within African health research ecosystems.

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